

Assessing the feasibility of cold-forming of automotive parts from quenched and partitioned martensitic stainless steels

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Sheet metal forming is among the most widely employed processes in manufacturing. Its economic feasibility relies on many factors, including the mechanical properties of the processed materials, energy efficiency of the metalforming processes and quality of the manufactured parts. This work focuses on developing a computational approach to assess the mechanical behavior of Quenched and Partitioned (QP) Martensitic Stainless Steels (MSSs) undergoing cold forming, aiming at the serial production of automotive parts. The Johnson-Cook (J-C) constitutive model and Forming Limit Diagram (FLD) are derived and validated for each alloy using the experimental data from tensile and Nakajima tests. From the simulated FLD, a theoretical Forming Limit Stress Diagram (FLSD) is calculated. The latter is used as a fracture criterion for the cold-forming process. Cold stamping of two automotive parts, B-pillar and tunnel, is modeled using the J-C constitutive model and the FLSD. It is demonstrated that the tunnel can be successfully cold-formed from all three studied steels. In contrast, extensive cracking is expected during the cold forming of the B-pillar from all materials. It is envisaged that these computational models can be employed for the assessment of any comparable part manufacturing procedure from the QP MSSs.

KEYWORDS

martensitic stainless steel, cold forming, Johnson-Cook model, forming limit diagram, forming limit stress diagram

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Given the increasing awareness of the effect of human activity on the environment [1], society is asking the industry to carry out better practices. One of the most affected by this paradigm change is the automotive industry, which contributes to pollutant emissions both in the manufacturing and service stages. Manufacturers have investigated different approaches to reduce carbon emissions, such as lightening the frame structure of the vehicle. This can be achieved using Advanced High Strength Steels (AHSS) [2]. With this strategy, emissions are reduced in both stages: 1) less material is required for the frame, less has to be produced; and 2) as the vehicle is lighter, less fuel is consumed during its service. The vehicle's frame fulfills a security function, preventing occupants from suffering any damage in a collision by absorbing impact energy and deforming in a controlled manner. Thus, the material chosen to lighten the structure must meet high mechanical requirements. Stainless steel offers a compromise between light-weighting, mechanical and functional properties to suit the aforementioned application. A shortcoming is the high cost of the traditionally used alloys that fulfill the requirements for the application. Highly corrosion-resistant austenitic stainless steels contain high amounts of chromium and nickel, alloying elements that increase the cost, especially the latter. Martensitic Stainless Steel (MSS) is another grade inside this family that does not require as much nickel in its composition. Hence, the alloy's price is lower than that of an austenitic one, although corrosion resistance is somewhat lower.

The mechanical properties of certain MSSs can be improved using the heat treatment called Quenching and Partitioning (QP), which stabilizes austenite to room temperature in order to promote the Transformation Induced Plasticity (TRIP) effect [3]. This heat treatment has been applied to carbon steels with successful results, generating a family named 'QP steels' [4]. QP steels belong to the third generation of AHSS, which mechanical properties put this generation between the First and the Second, as shown in Figure 1. The QP MSSs aim to achieve a similar combination of mechanical properties.

The main characteristics of MSS are their high strength and optimal corrosion resistance with a relatively low alloying content. The as-quenched microstructure of most MSSs is composed of a matrix of martensite laths, and they can present thin films of retained austenite between laths [6]. Their mechanical and application-related properties are determined by microstructure, which, in turn, strongly depends on the applied heat treatment. Therefore, tuning the heat treatment enables engineers to achieve a wide range of properties in these materials. The QP process has been applied to reach higher ductility levels without losing strength in MSSs. The material is austenitized, and then quenched to a temperature between the start and finish temperatures of the martensitic transformation, retaining an amount of austenite within the newly formed martensite. During the next partitioning step, the samples are heated to a higher temperature to facilitate the diffusion of carbon from the supersaturated martensite into the austenite. This increase of carbon in the austenite stabilizes it and allows it to remain in the final microstructure at room temperature. The presence of metastable austenite enables the TRIP effect during plastic deformation. It improves the material's strain hardening ability, resulting in enhanced ductility. A few publications focused on QP processing of AISI grades 410 and 420. Regarding grade 410, Tobata et al. [7] investigate the effect of silicon content and QP parameters on microstructure and strength-ductility balance, and Tsuchiyama et al. [8] study the effect of carbon content. In terms of grade 420, Huang et al. [9] focus on the impact of the heat treatment on the microstructural parameters; Yuan et al. [10] analyze the stability of retained austenite during plastic deformation; Mola and De Cooman [11] investigate the microstructure-property relationship; and Sierra-Soraluce et al. [12] study the effect of chemistry on the microstructure, tensile deformation behavior, and microstructure evolution during plastic deformation of QP treated MSSs. In these works, high volume fractions of retained austenite are achieved in the final microstructure: up to a 15% in 410 (low C, 0.12-0.13 wt.%) [7] and up to 57% in 420 (medium C, 0.47 wt. %) [9]. Such microstructures

FIGURE 1 Ashby plot, total elongation vs. ultimate tensile strength [5]. (For colour, please refer to online version.)

result in improved tensile behavior of MSS. In the 410 grade, while maintaining a similar level of strength (at ~ 1200 MPa), the tensile ductility is increased by 5% compared to the standard quenched and tempered state [8]. In the case of 420 grade, the same behavior is observed with ultimate tensile strengths ~ 1800 MPa [9].

Although the formability of QP MSSs has not been studied, a first gross estimate can be drawn up, taking the ductility. It is well known that formability is closely related to a material's ductility. As mentioned above, the ductility of MSS improves after QP treatment. For other types of AHSS, the positive effect of QP treatment on formability has been demonstrated for low-carbon steel [13] and medium carbon steel [14]. Independently, the potential of MSSs for cold-forming applications has already been proven with the cold-forming of diverse automotive parts [15]. Cold-forming has several advantages compared to hot forming. It is energy efficient and allows for high precision, high-quality surface finishes, and high-speed production. The main disadvantage of this process is the low level of geometry complexity achievable. The central objective of this work is to assess the feasibility of cold-forming automotive parts from QP MSSs. To achieve this objective, a computational approach, moderately based on experimental data, has been developed. The outcome of this approach is a set of numerical models that significantly reduce the number of required experiments and related material waste. In more detail, based on a limited collection of experimental data, the procedure involves a comparative selection of two distinct material constitutive models. The chosen model is then coupled with experimentally derived forming limit diagrams, which serve as a ductile fracture criterion. Through successive intermediate validations, these developments serve as computational tools for obtaining high-fidelity numerical models specifically designed for industrial cold-forming applications. These models were initially established as the primary goal of this study.

2 | JOHNSON-COOK MODEL IN FORMABILITY STUDIES

In this section, a comprehensive insight into the Johnson-Cook (J-C) constitutive model is given, including its mathematical formulation and the approach taken when using it for the development of formability simulations.

2.1 | Application of Johnson-Cook model in formability studies

The use of the J-C constitutive model to reproduce the mechanical behavior of materials undergoing forming processes is fairly standardized. In particular, Wang et al. [16] employ the mentioned equation to simulate the stamping process of preheated boron steel samples. A good match between simulated results and experimental data is found, thus enabling numerical prediction before performing the physical process at an industrial level. On the other hand, in another work [17] the authors analyze the prediction capabilities of the model regarding the simulation of a steel material when subjected to the cold roll-beating, finding that the data of the true stress generated during the simulated procedure are consistent with those obtained with experimental methods. Likewise, in [18] the authors find a good agreement of the numerical data with regard to the prediction of the behavior of copper and aluminum alloys when being processed through a cold wire drawing cycle, or in [19], where the authors explore the simulation of the oscillating cold forming process by using the J-C model coupled with different unloading models, finding that one of the combinations could successfully describe the experimentally observed deformation. It must be emphasized that while the J-C model is capable of simulating materials experiencing deformations under variable strain rate and temperature conditions, its application in scenarios where strain is the only variable does not diminish its simulation capabilities. In situations where only strain varies, as observed in previous studies [16–19] and the present paper, the J-C model is capable of independently handling this variable. This is due to the model's formulation, which accounts for the inherent independence of strain, strain rate, and temperature by representing them as separate factors in the equation.

Nevertheless, when employing a widely applicable strength model such as the J-C model in this case, it is essential to consider its use in conjunction with another constitutive equation that incorporates the material's fracture behavior. The strength model establishes the material's limits for failure under the given simulated conditions. In particular, a similar approach has already been used in the previous work by Panich et al. [20], where a yield model is coupled with the Forming Limit Diagram (FLD) and Forming Limit Stress Diagram (FLSD) fracture criteria to assess the formability of steel sheets under stamping processes, having as an outcome a successful prediction when comparing the data with those extracted from real experiments.

All of these works strengthen the initial hypothesis considered in this paper, relying on the employment of the aforementioned constitutive equation coupled with either a strain-based or a stress-based criterion to properly assess the different martensitic stainless steels under study when used in industrial cold forming.

2.2 | Johnson-Cook constitutive relations

The J-C constitutive model has been widely employed in the reproduction of the plastic behavior of metals under conditions of large strains, high strain rates and high temperatures. It is not considered to be a constitutive equation able to offer extremely accurate predictions for all the possible variable ranges, but among its advantages, it counts on fair robustness and its computational implementation is relatively simple. Due to this, it has been used over the last decades in a wide spectrum of applications: machining simulations [21]; hot stamping process [22]; and Charpy test simulations [23].

The J-C constitutive equation is one of the J_2 classical plasticity models, in which the yield stress σ_y is assumed to be of the form

$$\sigma_y = (A + B\varepsilon_p^n)(1 + C \log \dot{\varepsilon}_p^*) (1 - \Theta_*^m), \quad (1)$$

where there are three main terms. The first part refers to the quasi-static hardening, in which the initial yield stress, A , together with the parameters representing the strain hardening, B and the exponent n can be found, as well as the variable ε_p , representing the equivalent plastic strain. The second one is related to the hardening provoked by the strain rate effects, where the strain rate parameter, C , as well as the dimensionless plastic strain rate, $\dot{\varepsilon}_p^* = \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}_p}{\dot{\varepsilon}_{p0}}$, including $\dot{\varepsilon}_{p0}$ as a reference plastic strain rate chosen in accordance to the lowest experimental values expected, are found. Finally, the third term, which accounts for the effects of temperature, includes the thermal softening exponent, m , and also the so-called "homologous temperature", as

$$\Theta_* = \frac{\Theta_{exp} - \Theta_{room}}{\Theta_{melt} - \Theta_{room}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Theta_{exp} \equiv \Theta$ represents the experimental temperature at which the material is being modeled, Θ_{melt} is the melting temperature of the material and Θ_{room} is the ambient temperature for the minimum experimental reference.

3 | MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 | Materials and processing

Three alloys are selected for this study, and their chemical composition in weight percent are presented in Table 1. The first alloy (1) can be classified within the grade AISI 410, while the second alloy (2) falls in the grade AISI 420. The third alloy is a modified version of alloy 2, with an increased content in Mn and small additions of Ti and Nb. With the increased content of Mn, a stabilization of the austenitic phase is sought and the microalloying with Ti and Nb provides a grain refinement thanks to the formation of their nano-carbides. Slabs of casted material were hot rolled with a finishing temperature of 1000 °C. Then an annealing was performed for alloy 1 and 2 annealed at 740 °C for 24 h and air cooled; while alloy 3 was annealed at 700 °C for 24 h and furnace cooled. The final material had a form of sheets of 1.5 mm in thickness and 220-240 mm in width.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of the studied alloys in wt. %

ALLOY	C	Mn	Si	Cr	Ni	Al	N	Others
1	0.2	0.7	0.35	12.5	0.2	0.01	0.03	-
2	0.3	0.7	0.35	13.0	0.2	0.01	0.03	-
3	0.3	3.0	0.35	13.0	0.2	0.01	0.03	0.05 Nb + 0.05 Ti

Sheets of the selected alloys are QP treated using the parameters provided in Table 2. They were austenitized at 1100 °C for 15 minutes to dissolve the carbides present in the as-received material, with the exception of (Ti,Nb)C in alloy 3. This process also homogenized the distribution of alloying elements. The quenching temperatures for alloys 1 and 2 were chosen to yield the highest fraction of retained austenite in the final microstructure. For alloy 3, the quenching temperature was set to room temperature (30 °C) to investigate this specific processing route due to its industrial relevance, as the optimal quenching temperature was relatively close (62 °C). The quenching soaking

time was sufficient to ensure temperature homogenization across the sheet. The partitioning parameters used in this study were determined in previous research to provide the most favorable partitioning for the obtained retained austenite [12].

TABLE 2 QP treatment parameters of this study

ALLOY	Austenitization	Quenching	Partitioning
1		162 °C, 20 s	
2	1100 °C, 15 min	90 °C, 20 s	450 °C, 5 min
3		25 °C, 20 s	

3.2 | Mechanical testing

From the QP treated sheets, samples are machined for two different experimental tests: uniaxial tensile testing and Nakajima testing. For the tensile testing, standard dog bone samples (gauge length 50 mm and gauge width 12.5 mm) are machined with a 90 ° angle with the rolling direction.

Following the standard ASTM E8M [24], tensile test are carried out in an universal testing machine at room temperature and strain rate of $10^{-3} s^{-1}$. Three tensile specimens are tested per alloy. A representative stress-strain curve of each alloy is displayed in Figure 2. From these curves, the Yield Strength (YS), the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS), uniform elongation (ϵ_u) and elongation to fracture (ϵ_f) are obtained and are presented in Table 3.

FIGURE 2 Engineering stress-strain curves for the 3 alloys. (For colour, please refer to online version.)

TABLE 3 Extracted data from tensile curves.

ALLOY	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	ϵ_u (%)	ϵ_f (%)
1	996	1339	12.7	26.0
2	1040	1642	17.9	24.2
3	1015	1528	15.9	26.9

In the case of Nakajima testing, 5 geometries (two coupons per geometry) are machined for every alloy, ranging from (quasi) uniaxial to equibiaxial stress states. After removing the oxide layer with sand blasting, a square grid is applied to each specimen. The samples are deformed until fracture using a hydraulic press with a hemispherical punch of 100 mm diameter. Lubrication is used to reduce the friction between the punch and the sheet samples. The load versus displacement curves of selected specimens are recorded. Using Digital Image Correlation (DIC), the strain measurements are extracted from the deformed grid post-test. The FLC are then constructed for each alloy. The FLD is an extension of the FLC. These data are used to develop the Finite Element Method (FEM) models described in the coming sections.

3.3 | Microstructural characterization

The samples are characterized using Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD), and the resulting maps are collected in Figure 3. The volume fraction of retained austenite increases from 9.7 % in alloy 1 to 18.3 % in alloy 2 to 18.7 % in alloy 3. This trend is related to the increasing content of austenite-stabilizing alloying elements (C, Mn) [12].

Further analysis is carried out for alloy 3 (undeformed, Geometry 0), estimating its fresh martensite fraction according to the work [25] and collected in Table 4. The prior austenite grains (PAG) are reconstructed using the MTEX package for Matlab [26]. EDX analysis in TEM was performed in different areas of alloy 3, and no presence of Ti nor Nb was found in solid solution in the matrix. Given the small fraction of Ti and Nb, and the superior fraction of C, it is known and established that all of them have precipitated in the form of carbides (consuming a low amount of C along), as it was proven in our recent work, where a thorough microstructural characterization of the studied alloys was performed [12]. Similar observations were also reported for a Nb-microalloyed QP-treated carbon steel by Xia et al. [13].

The effects of the modifications of alloy 3 are here observed, achieving a higher fraction of retained austenite and showing a general reduction of the grain size, which is related to the controlled prior austenite grain size (from PAG size 38.3 μm in alloy 1, to 20.4 μm in alloy 3) via nanocarbides precipitation, as recently reported in [12].

Additionally, three geometries of alloy 3 are selected for their microstructural characterization (Geometries 1, 3 and 5). The same procedure applied to the undeformed material is used here again. The results are collected in Table 4, with the corresponding EBSD maps in Figure 4. The plastic strain (ϵ_{pl}) reported in Table 4 is calculated with the initial thickness of the sheet and the final one $\epsilon_{pl} = \ln(t_0/t)$. Based on these results, it is clear to see that the volume fraction decreases with increasing plastic strain. The retained austenite is transformed into fresh martensite (Fresh M) which may be identified as such or non-indexed (NI), hence why both of these fractions increase as well. The remaining retained austenite is the more stable one, hence its grain size decreases, but most importantly its aspect ratio. Similar microstructural evolution was also demonstrated by alloys 1 and 2.

FIGURE 3 EBSD band contrast maps of the QP treated alloys. In a green overlay, the retained austenite is highlighted. a) Alloy 1, b) Alloy 2, and c) Alloy 3. (For colour, please refer to online version.)

3.4 | Development of FEM models

FEM models are employed in this work to accomplish two objectives: Firstly, to replicate experimental tests and validate themselves by comparing the results with different material properties obtained from real data. Secondly, to predict the outcome of forming processes, specifically the cold stamping of industrial parts.

Nakajima experiments carried out with three different QP MSSs in the form of five different sample shapes are simulated, as shown in Figure 5, in order to validate the ductile fracture limits observed during the actual tests, being these expressed in the form of the equivalent plastic strain, ϵ_p , and the FLD curves. The latter referred simulated models are created employing the Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) software ABAQUS, in which the experiment is replicated by modeling the die, holder and the hemispheric punch parts as rigid 3D shells, being the first two fixed, holding the sample in place based on a penalty friction formulation with a coefficient of 0.02, while the punch moves vertically at a constant speed of 1.5 mm/s, as dictated by the ISO standards 12004-1 [27] and 12004-2 [28]. All the parts count on axisymmetric displacement boundary conditions so that only a quarter of the whole setup can be simulated, saving important computational effort. More in detail, each of the differently shaped quarter-sheet parts are modeled through deformable 3D shells, with meshes consisting of approximately 5500 linear-S4R elements, counting on 6 integration points equally distributed over the 1.5 mm thickness of the sheets. The simulations are solved by employing an explicit integration scheme assisted by mass scaling techniques, aiming at reducing the overall computational cost.

TABLE 4 Microstructural parameters of selected Nakajima samples of alloy 420ma.

ALLOY	Geom.	NI [%]	Martensite		Austenite			ϵ_{pl} [%]
			Fresh M [%]	Tempered M [%]	f [%]	d [μm]	a.r. [-]	
420ma	0	14.7	6.0	60.6	18.7	0.6 ± 0.5	2.8 ± 1.7	0
	1	19.7	11.5	59.9	8.9	0.4 ± 0.3	2.7 ± 1.4	13.5
	3	17.2	12.3	63.7	6.8	0.4 ± 0.4	2.4 ± 1.1	23.8
	5	21.4	17.8	54.4	6.4	0.4 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 1.1	26.5

The simulation of the behavior of each steel is approached from the plasticity point of view, considering two initial perspectives. The first relied on the use of the stress-strain curves recorded for each alloy during tensile tests carried out beforehand. While the second, and eventually the one which is chosen, is based on the use of the J-C constitutive model, whose parameters are obtained also employing the data from the latter experiments, with a similar method as the one shown in [29], and then validated employing the force vs. displacement curves extracted from the Nakajima tests. Insights on this matter are given below in this paper.

Thus, once the model is set, the Quantities of Interest (QoI) ϵ_p and the FLD curves are recorded in the simulations and compared with those acquired during the tests, therefore aiming at validating them. Subsequently, the extraction of the Forming Limit Stress Diagram (FLSD) curves for each material is conducted through simulations of Nakajima tests. This approach proves advantageous as it circumvents the high cost associated with attempting to obtain these curves directly through experimental procedures. Recording the entire deformation path in the failure region is necessary to calculate these values, as indicated by the Levy-Mises relation,

$$d\epsilon_{ij} = d\lambda s_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

where the tensor of incremental strain $d\epsilon_{ij}$ is proportional to the plastic slip $d\lambda$ and the tensor of deviatoric stress s_{ij} , which, in turn, depends on the non-incremental tensor of strain ϵ_{ij} .

Finally, after carrying out the extraction of this alternative fracture ductile criteria of the three steel materials through numerical methods, some relevant stamping simulations are performed, involving the cold stamping process of two industrial manufactured parts, namely the B-pillar and the central transmission tunnel of generic automobiles, being both representative examples of the standard usage and application of the materials studied.

4 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results derived from the simulations developed aiming at replicating the Nakajima experiments computationally are shown and discussed, specifically with a focus on the different theoretical procedures applied and the outcome arising from them.

4.1 | Approach to plasticity simulation: Johnson-Cook vs. traditional stress-strain curves

As mentioned previously, during the development of this work, two different approaches were initially considered when dealing with the method to simulate the plastic behavior of the material for the different Nakajima experiments that needed to be replicated numerically. Namely, these were the use of stress-strain curves extracted from the initial tensile tests and the utilization of the J-C model, which implies the additional finding of the corresponding material

FIGURE 4 EBSD band contrast maps of alloy 3 samples: undeformed and Nakajima geometries after testing. In a green overlay, the retained austenite is highlighted. (For colour, please refer to online version.)

parameters to describe the characteristics of the martensitic steel properly.

More in detail, when the first of them was employed, the tensile stress-strain data points taken from the quasi-static tensile tests were introduced as the plastic model within the ABAQUS models. Once the Nakajima tests models were run, the simulated force vs. displacement curves could be obtained and compared with those recorded during the actual tests. This way, it was observed that depending on the sample shape, and therefore, on the different stress states of uniaxial tension, plane strain or biaxial tension occurring during the tests, the fitting accuracy of the numerical data with respect to the actual data could notably vary, getting relative error percentages between the different curves in the range of 5 - 150 %. When trying to apply scaling factors to the stress-strain data to try to reduce the higher errors, the smaller ones were increased, not being able to improve the overall results.

Thus, a different approach had to be taken into account if the Nakajima tests were to be replicated with high fidelity. In particular, ABAQUS offers a variety of constitutive material models, among which the J-C equation is included. Thus, this relation has been considered to deal appropriately with the simulation of metals subjected to high strain, as is the case here, although any similar one, as it could be the Zerilli-Armstrong model or Arrhenius-type equations could be also considered for the same purposes. As a result of its use, each element stress state of the simulated Nakajima samples can be calculated in each simulation time step with a significantly higher precision than in the more rudimentary case of employing a tabulated relation of points uniquely taken from uniaxial tensile tests, which do not represent either the actual complex state and varying triaxiality occurring during the tests. This leads to

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 5 Nakajima test samples (1-5, from left to right) tested (a) and computational layout of Nakajima test using ABAQUS software (b).

the achievement of a better match between the experimental and simulated force-displacement curves obtained.

In order to be used, first, different material parameters need to be determined, carrying out a similar procedure as the one presented in [29]. Unfortunately, as merely quasi-static tests at room temperature were available, only the A , B and n parameters could be calculated, remaining thus C and m to be fixed, taking for them standard values found in the literature for the most similar martensitic steels regarding the chemical composition, assuming these to be the same for the three different materials [30]. In any case, neither high strain rates nor high temperatures are expected to take place during the industrial processes aimed at being simulated, therefore no major importance is considered to lie upon these values.

TABLE 5 Values employed for the three different alloys in every parameter and constant considering the J-C model.

Alloy	A	B	n	C	m	$\dot{\epsilon}_{p0}$	Θ_{room}	Θ_{melt}
1	985 MPa	523.22 MPa	0.282	0.02	0.8	$0.001 s^{-1}$	20 °C	1495 °C
2	1020 MPa	715.2 MPa	0.599	0.02	0.8	$0.001 s^{-1}$	20 °C	1495 °C
3	1030 MPa	424.6 MPa	0.287	0.02	0.8	$0.001 s^{-1}$	20 °C	1495 °C

Once fixed, all three alloys are simulated under the Nakajima test procedure, performing first the comparison between the force vs. displacement data extracted from them, employing both the J-C and the FLD curves as strength and fracture constitutive methods, and the actual data from the experiments.

In Figure 6 the latter comparison is shown for the extreme cases of stress state, taking these place when samples 1 and 5 are simulated (see Figure 5), having then uniaxial tension and equibiaxial tension conditions, respectively. It can be observed how the errors in both displacement to fracture and force exerted during the tests are relatively limited and even in all cases. In particular, the global average errors founds were 11.7 % and 14.9 %, respectively. It must be remarked that since the displacement to fracture has been assessed as very lowly dependent on the work absorbed by the samples during the simulations, only the maximum force, and not the whole loading curve, has been considered for the calculation of the latter error.

Analyzing these results, the error of 11.7 % obtained when simulating the displacement to fracture for all samples can tentatively be considered a success. The cracking phenomenon is highly complex, and errors within similar ranges are typically encountered when attempting to simulate such intricate physical processes. Regarding the error of 14.9 % obtained when simulating the maximum force exerted during the tests, it has been assessed that the significance of this factor for simulating a material's ductility is not as high as the importance of the displacement to fracture. Therefore, the consequences of this result are not considered to have a major impact on the simulations. This will be proved with the aid of the simulations of the next sections, where in spite of the fact of having observed higher maximum forces in the Nakajima numerical models, as shown in Figure 6, the simulated FLD curves obtained will be more conservative than those extracted from the real tests.

Bearing this analysis in mind, the previous results can be initially considered good enough to be able to assess the simulations as successful, provided that these will be further validated in the next sections of the document on the basis of subsequent and more complex tests.

(a) Sample 1

(b) Sample 5

(c) Sample 1

(d) Sample 5

(e) Sample 1

(f) Sample 5

FIGURE 6 Nakajima force vs. displacement data comparison between simulated and experimental tests for alloy 1 (a, b), alloy 2 (c, d), and alloy 3 (e, f). (For colour, please refer to online version.)

4.2 | Plastic strain distribution and FLD curves comparison in the Nakajima tested samples

After the previously demonstrated initial validation of the constitutive model for simulating the strength and fracture behavior of the different alloys, a more comprehensive comparison is conducted. This comparison focuses on the key data extracted from the Nakajima experiments, with the aim of fully validating the computational models. Specifically, the two considered QoI are the plastic equivalent strain (ε_p) prior to the fracture point as well as the FLD curves, which are considered as the most critical criteria for predicting the material's ability to withstand ductile damage during forming processes. Therefore, its validation in the computational case attains considerable importance to employ these models as future useful tools.

More specifically, for the validation of the simulated ε_p , the same procedure as the one used to extract the experimental data is employed in the simulations, taking the highest value registered in any of the sample's mesh elements after the fracture of the material has occurred.

Once checked all the comparative values for every test (e.g. Figure 7), it has been calculated that the global average error when considering the 15 cases for every alloy and sample shape is 32.7 %. It might be regarded as too large taking into consideration that the attainment of a high-fidelity model is one of the main goals in this work. However, it must be taken into account that the computational model tends to increase excessively the value of plastic strain in those elements close to the fractured ones, distorting in an artificial manner the extracted values of ε_p . This comparison raises concerns about the suitability of using this approach to validate the model due to the presence of this undesirable numerical side effect.

On the other hand, a second path is explored when comparing now the experimental and simulated FLD curves. Again, the standard criteria established in ISO 12004-2 [28], is replicated to find the latter. In this particular case the complexity increases, since in order to capture the major and minor principal strain values in each simulation it is necessary to take all the major and minor principal strain values from the deformed node elements, which are perpendicular to the fracture zone. Then, both series of data, experimental and simulated, are approximated by a second-degree equation employing the least squares minimization technique. Finally, the relevant data pair of each simulation test is taken as the greatest and lowest values of both maximum and minimum strain approximated curves, which should ideally take place in the same element node.

By performing this procedure and comparing the experimental and the simulated data, the FLD error results can be found. The pairs of curves are shown in Figure 8.

On the whole, upon examining these results, they can be considered partially successful, as there is generally a good agreement between the pairs of data. There is, however, a notable discrepancy in the case of alloy 3, where a significant gap exists between the simulated and the experimental curves. This mismatch is likely due to the absence of simulated data in the minor strain range from 0.0 to 0.08, which results in a loss of information regarding the actual fracture behavior of the material in that zone. When the global average error considering the three alloys is calculated, the outcome results in 13.9 %. This result has been notably affected by the large error found for alloy 3 (18.5 %), as previously explained, in contrast to those achieved for alloys 1 and 2 (12.4 % and 10.9 %, respectively), which are in a more common and acceptable range, considering the complex features of the ductile fracture phenomena aimed at being simulated in this paper. Also, it must be noted that the FLD curves found are, in theory, more conservative than the experimental ones. Nonetheless, it has been observed in posterior experimental testing that the experimental curves are, in some cases, too optimistic, finding that the fracture tends to occur before reaching the limits they predict. This would support the agreement of the simulated curves with the real behavior of the material.

In any case, the latter errors are considerably lower than the previous error found for the QoI ε_p comparison. This

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 7 Nakajima test comparison for ε_p , showing experimental (a) vs. computational (b) results, with maximum values of 0.29 and 0.343 marked with a white dot, respectively. (For colour, please refer to online version.)

FIGURE 8 Comparison of experimental and simulated FLD curves for alloy 1 (a), alloy 2 (b) and alloy 3 (c). (For colour, please refer to online version.)

is probably caused by the fact that not only a single point is taken to extract the given computational result but a set of them, having this a balancing effect on the numerical inaccuracies produced during the simulations. As an outcome, it can be considered that the simulated models are, on the whole, validated at the sight of the latter findings.

4.3 | FLSD vs FLD: improving fracture modeling

FLD ductile fracture criterion has been widely used for the simulation of forming processes in order to predict the onset of necking or fracture occurrence. Nonetheless, as pointed out by works such as [31], [32] or [33], some disagreements between these limit curves and the actual fracture behavior of metallic materials have been identified. Thus, these findings provide support for considering the use of the FLSD criterion based on stress as a relatively more favorable alternative, as indicated by these research studies. This criterion has been proved to bring some advantages, as the invariance of the limit curves themselves with respect to the thickness of the alloy sheets in comparison to the FLD criterion, or its notable capability to accurately predict necking in forming processes, as shown in [34] or [35], and further investigated in [36] or, also considering other kinds of extended stress-based FLC criteria, in [37].

The FLSD criterion relies on the concept of setting pairs of minor and major stresses shaping a limiting curve, such that if the stress state of the material is under it, the necking or fracture of the material will not happen.

The procedure employed to extract these ductile fracture limiting curves is based on computational methods, due to the restriction and complexity of the experimental equipment needed to calculate these values, as explained previously. Alternatively, validated models can be used to find them by taking maximum and minimum in-plane stresses present on the elements at the very moment in which necking is taking place on them. Thus, once this technique is employed, the values for the FLSD curves for each alloy are found. These are shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9 FLSD curves calculated for the studied QP MSSs. (For colour, please refer to online version.)

It can be observed how the different QP MSSs share very similar values for their forming limits, finding to a low degree very few discrepancies when reaching high minor stresses. Also, it must be noted that the fluctuations on each of the curves are due to the simulated nature of the extracted data and the numerical variations obtained in each of the elements from which the maximum and minimum values are sampled. Each of the QP MSSs' FLSD curves, and

thus, the simulated alloys' forming limits found, will be computationally tested when performing the numerical tests of sheet cold stamping for the manufacturing of usual car parts in the next section. This is regarded as a first testing bench for the proper prediction of the industrial procedure feasibility before any actual part gets physically into the assembly line.

4.4 | Feasibility assessment of MSS for manufacturing of automotive parts by cold stamping

Aiming at testing the ductility limits of the material when undergoing cold forming processes, the simulation of the stamping procedure as part of the manufacturing of two different automotive parts has been numerically replicated, namely the B-pillar and the central transmission floor tunnel of a generic and standard car.

As observed in Figure 10, the complexity related to the shape of both parts is uneven, since the pillar possesses a surface filled with numerous bends of a small radius and a much more intricate geometry in general in comparison to the tunnel part, subjecting the material to higher strains and stresses during the stamping, which can have critical consequences towards the success of the process. This makes the B-pillar a more challenging geometry for a high strength alloy, while the tunnel part represents, in relative terms, a moderately difficult one.

For these simulations, all three alloys are employed, making use of the already validated data to set up the ABAQUS models (Figure 11). In particular, they consist of a lower rigid die, fixed on the lower part, acting as the base, and an upper rigid die, moving at a standard speed of 1.25 mm/s, whereas the martensitic alloy sheet with 1.25 mm thickness is positioned in between both at the start of the simulations, counting on approximately 38000 linear-S3R elements. The rest of the setup features for these models are replicated from those already described in Section 3.4. No guide pins are considered in the simulation setup, as the misalignment of the sheet during the deformation process is negligible. In the same way, the appearance of wrinkling is practically avoided without any additional parts due to the action of the forces exerted by the dies themselves as the part gets pressed.

The results of the different simulations for both parts can be observed in Figures 12 and 13.

As shown in the latter, no significant differences with regard to the final results considering the different alloys can be reported, as the widespread fracturing occurring in the run of the B-pillar is not avoided for any of the three metal materials. Likewise, the outcome of the models replicating the stamping process of the tunnel part is quite similar, at least in what concerns the non-onset of cracks in the sheets for each QP MSS case, having this already been predicted in view of the similarities observed in the found FLSD curves. Similarly, as expected due to the difference in complexity of the parts, there is a clear contrast between the forming processes of both car pieces, being far from successful in the case of the B-pillar, whereas the tunnel part does not show any fully damaged element, therefore according to these outcomes it could be foreseen that, under the same cold stamping conditions, only the production of one of the latter seems feasible. It is important to notice that the springback issues are relevant during metal forming of stainless steels [39]. This topic has been out of scope of our article, since it is impossible to consider all the issues related with metalforming process. However, it should be noted that there is a body of research in the current literature clearly showing the springback effect can be significantly reduced in martensitic steel sheets by electrically single-pulsed current [40].

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 10 Actual final shape of the automotive parts whose stamping process is simulated, a) B-pillar and b) tunnel [38].

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 11 Setup of the ABAQUS simulation models for both parts, a) B-pillar and b) tunnel.

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 12 Final results of B-pillar stamping simulations for alloy 1 (a, b), alloy 2 (c, d), and alloy 3 (e, f). (For colour and supplementary video, please refer to online version.)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

FIGURE 13 Final results of transmission tunnel stamping simulations for alloy 1 (a, b), alloy 2 (c, d), and alloy 3 (e, f). alloy 1 (a, b), alloy 2 (c, d), and alloy 3 (e, f). (For colour and supplementary video, please refer to online version.)

5 | CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a fully computational approach has been developed on the basis of experimental data extracted from quasi-static tensile and Nakajima tests, employing them to feed the modeling of cold forming processes applied on three different martensitic alloys, aiming at replicating them numerically, getting thus a high-fidelity tool to predict their feasibility, supporting in advance a potential future experimental campaign.

In particular, the J-C model has been coupled with FLSD curves to simulate the behavior during the plastic straining phase and later potential fracture of the material, extracting the main values of both methods from the above-mentioned experimental sources. The resulting models have been validated to a satisfactory degree with complementary data from the same actual physical tests, being finally used to replicate the expected outcome as a result of performing a cold stamping process for the manufacturing of two widespread automotive metal parts.

The output of the latter simulations seems to fit reasonably well with the anticipated behavior according to the characteristics observed during the modeling process, predicting a low ductility, and therefore, poor capacity to withstand the forming process when trying to shape complex surfaces cluttered with small bending radii. These expectations are also well in line with the previous experimental ductility performance of the different alloys witnessed during the Nakajima tests campaign. Nonetheless, it will be necessary to validate these numerical stamping runs with physical tests to fully confirm the usefulness of the models.

Altogether, the procedure is relatively fast and not heavily dependent on experimental data, which is something considered positive since these data must be necessarily extracted from expensive physical tests. Despite this simplification in the procedure, the method employed has been proven to be reliable in comparison to others when examined in previous research work.

The modeling shows extensive cracking during the cold forming of the B-pillar for all the three studied alloys. In contrast, no single damage element was detected in the case of cold forming of the tunnel part for any of the three alloys. Therefore, producing the tunnel parts from the QP treated MSSs seems feasible.

Finally, the proposed approach can be easily applied to predict the formability of other complex shape parts made of QP treated MSSs.

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Availability of data and materials

Data will be made available on request.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Table of Contents

This study developed a computational approach to simulate cold-forming processes on three different martensitic stainless steels using experimental data. The simulations were validated with Nakajima tests and used to replicate the outcome of a cold stamping process for two automotive parts. The simulations predicted extensive cracking during the cold-forming of a B-pillar but no damage for a tunnel. This approach can be used to predict the formability of other complex-shaped parts made of martensitic stainless steel. The procedure is fast and not heavily dependent on expensive experimental data.